

1 **Multivitamin supplementation is associated with greater adequacy of gestational weight**
2 **gain among pregnant women in Tanzania**

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35 Tanzania; Institute of Medicine

36 **Abbreviations**

37 BMI Body mass index

38 GWG Gestational weight gain

39 IOM Institute of Medicine

40 LMICs Low- and middle-income countries

41 UNIMMAP United Nations International Multiple Micronutrient Antenatal Preparation

42 **Clinical trial registry:** This trial was registered at ClinicalTrials.gov number as NCT00197548.

43 **Abstract**

44 **Background** Gestational weight gain (GWG) is a modifiable risk factor associated with adverse
45 birth outcomes. Studies have shown that the provision of multiple micronutrient supplements to
46 pregnant women reduces the risk of low birthweight. However, the effect of multiple
47 micronutrient supplements on GWG has been understudied.

48 **Objective** We examined the effect of daily supplementation of pregnant women with
49 multivitamins on GWG in relation to the GWG recommendation by the IOM.

50 **Methods** Pregnant women with gestational age between 12 to 27 weeks were randomized to
51 receive daily multivitamins or placebo until delivery. Weight was measured at enrollment and
52 every follow-up visit. Percent adequacy of GWG was calculated as actual GWG divided by the
53 recommended GWG according to the IOM recommendation. Binary outcomes included severely
54 inadequate (<70%), inadequate (<90%), and excessive GWG ($\geq 125\%$). The analysis included
55 7573 women with singleton pregnancies. Multiple linear regression models were used to
56 examine the association between multivitamins supplementation and percent adequacy of GWG,
57 and log-binomial models were used for binary outcomes.

58 **Results** The mean percent adequacy of GWG was 96.7% in the multivitamin arm and 94.4% in
59 the placebo arm with mean difference of 2.3% (95% CI: 0.3%, 4.2%; $p = 0.022$). Compared to
60 women in the placebo arm, those who received multivitamins had a lower risk of severely
61 inadequate GWG (RR, 0.90; 95% CI, 0.83, 0.97; $p = 0.008$) and inadequate GWG (RR, 0.95;
62 95% CI, 0.91, 0.99; $p = 0.018$). No significant difference was found in excessive GWG.

63 **Conclusions** Multivitamin supplementation increased GWG and reduced the risk of severely
64 inadequate and inadequate GWG among pregnant women in Tanzania. Together with previously

65 reported beneficial effects of the supplements on birth outcomes in low- and middle-income
66 countries (LMICs), our findings support scaling up the use of prenatal supplements that include
67 multivitamins in addition to iron and folic acid.

68 **Introduction**

69 Maternal weight gain during pregnancy has been associated with adverse maternal and birth
70 outcomes (1, 2). Previous studies have shown that lower gestational weight gain (GWG)
71 increases the risk of low birthweight and small for gestational age at birth, and greater GWG was
72 associated with higher risks of large for gestational age and macrosomia (3-6). Both lower and
73 higher GWG have been associated with increased risk of preterm birth (2, 3). In addition, women
74 who gain excessive weight during pregnancy may experience various adverse maternal
75 outcomes, including complications during labor, increased risk of cesarean delivery, and
76 subsequent maternal obesity and cardiovascular disorders (1, 2).

77 In 2009, the Institute of Medicine (IOM) reexamined the recommendations for weight gain
78 during pregnancy stratified by pre-pregnancy maternal body mass index (BMI) (2). These
79 recommendations were entirely based on studies from high-income countries. Data on GWG
80 from low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) are limited (7). A recent analysis using data
81 from Demographic and Health Surveys estimated that the average total GWG in sub-Saharan
82 Africa and south Asia ranged between 6 and 7 kg, only about half the IOM's minimum
83 recommendation for normal weight women (8). Achieving optimal GWG may not only
84 improves immediate birth outcomes but also has many potential long-term benefits. Increasingly
85 evidence shows that optimal GWG is associated with reduced risks of postpartum weight
86 retention, infant mortality, as well as child overweight and obesity later in life (9, 10).

87 Provision of multiple micronutrient supplements to pregnant women has been consistently
88 associated with improved birth outcomes, including small-for-gestational-age births and low
89 birthweight, in LMICs (11-13). However, evidence linking multiple micronutrient supplements
90 and maternal weight gain is limited and inconsistent. Using data from a randomized controlled

91 trial conducted among pregnant women in Tanzania, we aimed to examine the effect of prenatal
92 multivitamin supplements on the adequacy of GWG based on the IOM recommendations. The
93 analysis was based on current knowledge level that compared to iron and folic acid only,
94 maternal multiple micronutrient supplements including iron and folic acid might improve birth
95 outcomes among malnourished pregnant women in LMICs (11). The results from the analysis
96 will help us better understand the beneficial effect of the supplements on birth outcomes, which
97 has been observed from the same data in Tanzania (14) as well as other randomized controlled
98 trials (15-17), and inform identification of effective prenatal nutritional intervention to achieve
99 optimal GWG in LMICs.

100 **Methods**

101 **Study population**

102 The current analysis used data from pregnant women who were enrolled in a double-blind,
103 randomized, placebo-controlled trial in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, between August 1, 2001, and
104 July 31, 2004 (ClinicalTrials.gov number, NCT00197548) (14). The eligibility for the original
105 trial included a negative test for HIV infection, a plan to stay in Dar es Salaam until delivery and
106 for at least 1 year after delivery, and an estimated gestational age between 12 and 27 weeks at
107 enrollment. Eligible women were randomly assigned to receive a daily oral dose of either a
108 multivitamin supplement or placebo from the time of enrollment until 6 weeks after delivery.
109 The supplements included 20 mg of thiamin, 20 mg of riboflavin, 25 mg of vitamin B-6, 100 mg
110 of niacin, 50 µg of vitamin B-12, 500 mg of vitamin C, 30 mg of vitamin E, and 0.8 mg of folic
111 acid. All tablets were commercially manufactured by Tishcon Corp, the supplement tablets and
112 placebo were similar in shape, size, and color. Adherence to the assigned treatment was
113 calculated as the number of tablets that were absent from the returned bottles divided by the total

114 number of tablets the participant should have taken. All women, irrespective of the assigned
115 study regimen, were given daily doses of iron (60 mg of elemental iron) and folic acid (0.25 mg)
116 according to Tanzanian antenatal care guidelines. All women were also provided with malaria
117 prophylaxis in the form of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine tablets at 20 weeks and 30 weeks of
118 gestation. Ethics approval for the trial was obtained from the institutional review boards of
119 Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, and Harvard
120 School of Public Health in Boston, MA, USA. Written informed consent was obtained from all
121 women.

122 **Data collection**

123 All women completed a baseline questionnaire that included their socio-demographic
124 characteristics, reproductive and medical history, smoking and alcohol consumption. We
125 constructed a baseline wealth index based on household asset ownership (e.g., television,
126 refrigerator, radio, sofa, and fan) using principal component analysis (18). Participants had study
127 visits by medical providers monthly until 32 weeks of gestation, then every two weeks until 36
128 weeks of gestation, and then weekly until 6 weeks after delivery. At baseline, research nurses
129 measured maternal height to the nearest 0.1 cm using a stadiometer with headcovers and shoes
130 removed. Weight was measured at baseline and every follow-up visit to the nearest 100 g using
131 balanced scales with the participant wearing light clothing without shoes.

132 **Estimation of the first-trimester weight**

133 Because pregnant women with gestation age between 12-27 weeks were enrolled in the trial,
134 majority of study participants (98%) did not have weight measures in the first trimester. For
135 women enrolled after 14 weeks of gestational age, we developed a model to impute their weight
136 at 9 weeks of gestation using restricted cubic spline models; we chose this timepoint because it is

137 the starting anchor used by INTERGROWTH-21st GWG standards (19). In another study
138 sample where the first-trimester weight was available for each pregnant woman, the correlation
139 coefficient between imputed weight from the model and observed weight at early pregnancy was
140 0.96, and the absolute difference was within 2 kg for 77% of the women participants. The details
141 of the model development, selection and validation have been published elsewhere (20).
142 Body mass index (BMI) was calculated as the first-trimester weight (predicted or observed) in
143 kilograms divided by square of height in meters. Women were classified as being underweight
144 (BMI <18.5 kg/m²), normal weight (BMI 18.5 to 24.9 kg/m²), overweight (BMI 25 to 29.9
145 kg/m²) or obese (BMI ≥30 kg/m²) based on the World Health Organization criteria (21). For
146 participants who were <20 years of age at enrolment, we used the World Health Organization
147 BMI-for-age growth references to classify adolescents as underweight (<-2 SD), normal weight
148 (-2 SD to <1 SD), overweight (1 SD to <+2 SD) or obese (≥+2 SD) (22).

149 **Outcomes**

150 **Percent adequacy of GWG**

151 First, total GWG for each woman was calculated by subtracting the predicted or observed first
152 trimester weight from the weight value measured at the last follow-up visit during pregnancy.

153 Second, following IOM 2009 recommendation (2), we estimated the expected weight gain for
154 each woman at the time of their last observed weight measure were taken using the following
155 formula:

156

157 Recommended GWG = expected first trimester total weight gain + [(gestational age at the last
158 weight measurement – 13^{6/7} week (equivalent to 13.86 weeks)) x recommended rate of GWG for
159 the second and third trimester by BMI category].

160
161 The expected first trimester total weight gain was assumed to be 2 kg for underweight and
162 normal weight women, 1 kg for overweight women, and 0.5 kg for obese women; and the
163 recommended rates of GWG for the second and third trimesters were 0.51, 0.42, 0.28 and 0.22
164 kg/wk for underweight, normal-weight, overweight, and obese women, respectively (2).
165 Finally, the percent adequacy of GWG was calculated by dividing the actual GWG by the
166 expected GWG at the last observed weight measurement, multiplied by 100. This is a continuous
167 measure that has been used in a previous study (23). We further categorized percent adequacy of
168 GWG into binary outcome measures. Inadequate GWG was defined as percent adequacy of
169 GWG < 90%, severely inadequate GWG as percent adequacy of GWG < 70%, and excessive
170 GWG as percent adequacy of GWG > 125%. The cut points 90% and 125% are corresponding
171 to the lower and upper limits of the recommended total weight gain during pregnancy by IOM
172 guideline. The recommend range is 12.5 to 18kg for women who are underweight (BMI <18.5
173 kg/m²), 11.5 to 16kg for normal weight (18.5 to 24.9 kg/m²), 7 to 11.5kg for overweight (25 to
174 29.9 kg/m²) and 5 to 9kg for obese (BMI ≥30 kg/m²) (2).

175
176 Using a similar strategy we developed trimester-specific outcome measures (e.g., percent
177 adequacy of GWG within the second and third trimesters) for study participants who had at least
178 two weight measures within a specific trimester. Corresponding binary outcomes, including
179 inadequate, severely inadequate, and excessive GWG, were created for the second and third
180 trimester, respectively, as well.

181

182 We also used the INTERGROWTH-21 gestational weight gain standards to derive GWG z-
183 score.(19) Since the currently available GWG equation for expected weight gain is meant for
184 normal weight women, we restricted this outcome to normal-weight women only.

185 **Statistical analysis**

186 For the current analysis, we only included women with singleton pregnancies who had at least
187 one weight measurement during the pregnancy. We excluded observations (not participants)
188 with implausible weight value (defined as being below 30 kg or above 120 kg) at any point
189 during pregnancy. Subject characteristics were summarized using mean and standard deviation
190 (SD) for continuous variables and frequency (percentage) for categorical variables by
191 intervention arm. We used multiple linear regression models to estimate mean difference and
192 95% confidence intervals (CIs) in percent adequacy of GWG and GWG z-score between arms.
193 We used log-binomial models or modified Poisson regression with robust standard error to
194 estimate the relative risks and 95% CIs of binary outcomes associated with prenatal multivitamin
195 supplements. In univariate analysis, we only included prenatal multivitamin supplements as
196 independent variable in the models. In multivariable analyses, we adjusted for baseline
197 characteristics including maternal age, gestational age at enrolment, household wealth index,
198 maternal education, parity, maternal stature, maternal anemia, smoking, and hypertension status.
199 All the covariates were selected based on their inclusion in previous analyses from the same trial
200 and from the literature (11, 24). In secondary analyses, we examined whether the covariates
201 mentioned above as well as infant sex and adherence to regimen modified the effects of prenatal
202 multivitamin supplements on GWG. Infant sex was selected as a potential effect modifier based
203 on results from previous studies (11, 15). Two-tailed p-values <0.05 were considered significant.
204 All statistical analyses were performed using SAS version 9.4 (SAS Institute).

205

206 **Results**

207 Among the 8428 pregnant women randomized in the trial, 7573 were singletons with at least one
208 weight measurements before delivery (Supplementary Figure 1). At baseline, more than half
209 (56%) of pregnant women were less than 25 years old, one third were enrolled before 20 weeks
210 of gestational age, and about 80% had ≤ 7 years of education. Pregnant women in multivitamin
211 and placebo arms did not differ in age, marital status, gestational age, parity, education,
212 household wealth, and nutritional status measured by body mass index, maternal stature, or
213 hemoglobin concentrations. The study arms were similar with respect to adherence, with mean of
214 88% and median of 96% (Table 1).

215 The mean percent adequacy of GWG was 96.7% in the multivitamin arm and 94.4% in the
216 placebo arm, with a crude mean difference of 2.3% (95% CI: 0.3%, 4.2%; $p=0.022$). In
217 multivariate analysis adjusted for potential confounders, the association persisted with a mean
218 difference of 2.1% (95% CI: 0.2%, 4.0%; $p=0.029$). Multivitamin supplementation reduced the
219 risks of severely inadequate GWG and inadequate GWG. In the multivitamin arm 910 women
220 (24.0%) had severely inadequate GWG versus 1005 (26.6%) in the placebo arm. Compared to
221 women who received placebo, those in the multivitamin arm had a 10% lower risk of severely
222 inadequate GWG (RR,0.90; 95% CI,0.83,0.97); the risks of inadequate GWG were 49.5% in the
223 multivitamin arm and 52.3% in the placebo arm (RR,0.95; 95% CI,0.91,0.99). No significant
224 difference was found in excessive GWG between multivitamin and placebo arms (19.2% in
225 multivitamin versus 17.8% in placebo; RR, 1.08; 95% CI 0.98, 1.19). In multivariate analysis
226 after adjusting for the potential confounders, the effect of multivitamin supplements on severely

227 inadequate GWG, inadequate GWG and excessive GWG did not change appreciably compared
228 to the univariate analyses (Table 2).

229 We further investigated the effect of prenatal multivitamin supplements on trimester specific
230 GWG. In the second trimester, women in the multivitamin arm had a greater percent adequacy of
231 GWG (90.5% vs 86.5%) compared to women in the placebo arm, but the difference was not
232 statistically significant ($p=0.12$); no significant associations were found between multivitamin
233 and any of the binary outcomes including inadequate GWG, severely inadequate GWG or
234 excessive GWG in the second trimester. In the third trimester, women in the multivitamin arm
235 were associated with a 4.0% increase in GWG percent adequacy (92.7% vs 88.7%; $P=0.09$). In
236 addition, GWG was associated with a 6% reduced risk of having severely inadequate GWG (RR,
237 0.94; 95% CI, 0.89- 1.00; $P=0.042$), and a nonsignificant 3% reduction in risk of inadequate
238 GWG (RR, 0.97; 95% CI, 0.92, 1.01; $P=0.11$) in the third trimester (Table 3).

239 Among women with normal BMI at baseline, the mean (SD) of GWG z-score based on
240 INTERGROWTH-21 was -0.49 SD (0.98) in the multivitamin arm and -0.54 SD (0.96) in the
241 placebo arm; the mean difference was 0.05 (95% CI, -0.01,0.11; $P=0.08$).

242 The effect of multivitamin on GWG percent adequacy, and the binary outcomes of inadequate
243 GWG, severely inadequate GWG, and excessive GWG was not modified by any of the following
244 potential effect modifiers, including adherence to regimen, maternal age, gestational age at
245 randomization, parity, maternal BMI, maternal stature, maternal anemic status, maternal
246 education, household wealth index, maternal hypertension, smoking status, and infant sex (Table
247 4 and Supplementary Table 1)

248

249 **Discussion**

250 In the current analysis, we found that about 50% of the study participants experienced inadequate
251 GWG, and 25% experienced severely inadequate GWG during pregnancy. This finding is
252 consistent with a recent meta-analysis of studies from sub-Saharan Africa, in which the authors
253 reported that the percentage of inadequate GWG, defined according to IOM recommendation,
254 was > 50% in 9 of the 16 studies (5). Another study from Bangladesh reported that 74% of
255 pregnant women had inadequate GWG (6). We also found that pregnant women who received
256 multivitamin supplementation had greater GWG and reduced risks of inadequate GWG and
257 severely inadequate GWG compared to those who were in the placebo arm. Multivitamin
258 supplementation during pregnancy had no effect on excessive GWG.

259 Limited information has been reported on the effect of prenatal multiple micronutrient
260 supplements on GWG among pregnant women, and when this question was examined the results
261 were not consistent. A trial from Ghana found that there was no difference in GWG measures
262 between pregnant women who received multiple micronutrient supplement and those who
263 received iron and folic acid supplement (23). Another trial conducted in Mexico similarly
264 reported that multiple micronutrient supplements did not increase weight gain during pregnancy
265 compared to iron supplements only (25). However, results from two trials in Tanzania
266 conducted among HIV-negative women (26) and HIV-infected women (27), demonstrated that
267 prenatal multiple micronutrient supplements were associated with a greater weight gain during
268 pregnancy. The discrepancy could be due to the difference in study population and intervention
269 doses. The doses of multiple micronutrient supplements used in both trials conducted in
270 Tanzania were much higher, containing 6-10 times of the recommended dietary allowance
271 (RDA) for vitamin C and B vitamins, and twice RDA for vitamin E, compared to only 1 to 2
272 RDA in the trials conducted in Ghana and Mexico. Results from trials in Nepal and Bangladesh

273 have brought up the concern that single RDA regimens may be suboptimal in settings of
274 widespread malnutrition and have not resulted in correction of micronutrient deficiencies (28,
275 29).

276 The current study aimed to examine the effect of multivitamin supplements on GWG according
277 to IOM recommendation. Compared to the previous analysis in which direct weight measures
278 were used, the current analysis focused on GWG percent adequacy, which was imputed based on
279 actual weight gain and IOM recommendation. Specifically, noting that in most prenatal cohorts
280 in low and middle-income settings (including our study population) most women do not have a
281 record of pre-pregnancy weight, we have imputed gestational weight in the first trimester by
282 applying a method that our team has developed (20), and that allowed us to estimate gestational
283 weight gain. We used this GWG estimate to compare against the IOM guidelines and our
284 outcomes are independent of gestational age at the time of weight measure. We then classified
285 the continuous outcome into severely inadequate, inadequate, and excessive GWG, and further
286 examined the effect multivitamin supplements on these binary outcomes and assessed effect
287 modifiers of the supplements. Furthermore, we used the INTERGROWTH-21 gestational weight
288 gain standards that were published in 2016 to derive GWG z-score and re-examined the effect of
289 the supplements on GWG among normal weight women.

290 Our current results that multivitamin supplementation was associated with a greater GWG are
291 consistent with the previous findings on birth outcomes in the same trial (14). Several meta-
292 analyses have been conducted to summarize the effect of prenatal multiple micronutrient
293 supplements on birth outcomes (11, 12, 30-32), and it has been consistently concluded that the
294 provision of multiple micronutrient supplements including iron and folic acid reduced the risks
295 of low birthweight, compared to provision of iron and folic acid only, or provision of iron alone.

296 In response to the accumulating evidence from LMICs on the beneficial effect of multiple
297 micronutrient supplements during pregnancy on low birthweight, in 2020, the WHO changed
298 their recommendation on multiple micronutrient supplements in pregnancy from “not
299 recommended” to “recommended in the context of rigorous research” (33).

300 The components of weight gain in early pregnancy are primarily maternal fat deposition, total
301 body water accretion, and placental and other tissue development, whereas weight gain in later
302 pregnancy is thought to be more related to fetal growth (2). Previous studies suggested that
303 GWG during the first and second trimesters had a stronger effect on birthweight than GWG that
304 occurred in the third trimester (1, 34). In the current analysis, we examined the effect of
305 multivitamin supplementation on cumulative GWG by trimester and most of our results were not
306 statistically significant except for severely inadequate GWG in the third trimester. This may be
307 due to limited statistical power of these trimester-specific analyses because women participants
308 had to have at least two weight measures within a specific trimester to be included in the analysis
309 for that trimester.

310 We did not find that the effect of prenatal multivitamin supplements on GWG was modified by
311 adherence to the regimen; this is perhaps because the overall adherence was high (median value
312 96.4%, interval quarter range 84%, 100%). The low variance in adherence resulted in small
313 difference in effect size between women with adherence <95% and those with adherence \geq 95%,
314 and we perhaps lacked enough power to detect that small difference. The prevalence of
315 hypertension and smoking were very low in the study population, and we were likely under
316 powered to detect any effect modification by these factors.

317 There are several plausible mechanisms through which multivitamins could improve GWG.
318 First, multivitamin supplementation may improve maternal immune function, leading to reduced

319 risk of infections, and any adverse effects of these on maternal weight (35, 36). Second,
320 multivitamins may increase food intake by influencing peptide hormone levels and
321 neurotransmitters that affect satiety and appetite (37, 38). Third, micronutrients included in the
322 supplements, such as vitamin C, B-vitamins, and iron, are involved in protein and energy
323 metabolism, DNA and RNA synthesis, and cell division, which may directly improve fetal
324 development and growth leading to higher GWG (39-42). Antioxidants, including vitamins C
325 and E, protect against free radical generation and damage caused by increased oxidative stress
326 associated with pregnancy (43), which have also been associated with low birthweight and
327 preterm birth (44).

328 There are several strengths in the current study. First, it was aimed to examine the effect of
329 multiple micronutrient supplements on GWG in relation to IOM recommendations. Previous
330 epidemiologic studies of GWG often used total GWG in kilogram or average rate of GWG,
331 which may be biased due to their correlation with gestation duration (45, 46). By using percent
332 adequacy of GWG which is independent of gestational duration, our findings could be explained
333 as the effect of multivitamin supplementation on GWG beyond its possible effect on gestation
334 duration. Furthermore, since pre-pregnancy BMI is one of the main determinants of GWG (3,
335 47), findings on total weight gain or rate of weight gain from different studies might not be
336 comparable if there were large differences in pre-pregnancy BMI across studies. Finally, the
337 current analysis has a large sample size with maternal weight measures during pregnancy
338 compared to prior studies, although our statistical power for trimester-specific analyses and
339 assessment of effect modification of supplements was possibly limited. Other limitations of this
340 study should be noted as well. Because participants were enrolled after their pregnancies were
341 confirmed, pre-pregnancy BMI was not available in the current study. However, since pre-

342 pregnancy BMI is required to calculate the recommended weight gain based on IOM and
343 INTERGROWTH-21st recommendations, we used BMI measured in the first trimester as a
344 substitute for pre-pregnancy BMI given that weight gain during the first trimester is minimal. For
345 women who did not have weight measure during the first trimester we developed and validated a
346 statistical modeling approach to estimate weight at 9 weeks of gestational age using weight
347 measures later during the second trimester. The methodology approach has been published (20).
348 In conclusion, our results demonstrate that the provision of multivitamin supplementation to
349 pregnant women improves GWG in relation to IOM recommendation. This finding provides
350 additional evidence to support the recently updated WHO guidelines on prenatal multiple
351 micronutrient supplements. Future studies should focus on implementation research to evaluate
352 acceptability, feasibility, and cost-effectiveness of switching to multiple micronutrient
353 supplements from iron and folic acid supplements only in target pregnant women population.

354

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358 computations and analysis; EL: draft the manuscript; EL and WWF: have primary responsibility
359 for the final content of the manuscript; and all authors: read and approved the final manuscript.
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Table 1. Characteristics of pregnant women by intervention arms (n=7573)

	Multivitamins	
	(n=3797)	Placebo (n=3776)
	Mean (SD) or n (%)	Mean (SD) or n (%)
Woman's age at randomization, y	25.2 (5.1)	25.0 (5.0)
<25	2102 (55.6%)	2125 (56.6%)
≥25	1682 (44.4%)	1627 (43.4%)
Marital status		
Married or cohabiting	3339 (88.5%)	3302 (88.3%)
Unmarried	435 (11.5%)	436 (11.7%)
Gestational age at randomization, wk	21.3 (3.4)	21.2 (3.5)
<20	1277 (33.6%)	1286 (34.1%)
≥20	2520 (66.4%)	2490 (65.9%)
Parity		
0	1741 (46.0%)	1711(45.6%)
≥ 1	2041 (54.0%)	2039 (54.4%)
BMI at first trimester (observed or imputed) ¹	22.7 (3.9)	22.7 (4.0)
Underweight	407 (10.7%)	391 (10.4%)
Normal weight	2499 (65.8%)	2473 (65.5%)
Overweight or obesity	891 (23.5%)	912 (24.1%)
Maternal stature, cm	155.6 (6.0)	155.4 (5.9)
<150	602 (15.9%)	589 (15.6%)

	Multivitamins	
	(n=3797)	Placebo (n=3776)
	Mean (SD) or n (%)	Mean (SD) or n (%)
≥ 150	3195 (84.1%)	3187 (84.4%)
Maternal anemia ²	10.2 (1.5)	10.2 (1.6)
Yes	2205 (67.9%)	2161 (66.5%)
No	1045 (32.1%)	1089 (33.5%)
Household wealth less than median		
Yes	1850 (48.9%)	1832 (48.7%)
No	1937 (51.1%)	1931 (51.3%)
years of education, y		
0-4	434 (11.5%)	409 (10.9%)
5-7	2479 (65.5%)	2538 (67.6%)
8-11	667 (17.6%)	623 (16.6%)
≥ 12	204 (5.4%)	184 (4.9%)
Current smoking		
Yes	6 (0.2%)	14 (0.4%)
No	3777 (99.8%)	3743 (99.6%)
Hypertension		
Yes	155 (4.1%)	148 (3.9%)
No	3642 (95.9%)	3628 (96.1%)
Adherence to treatment <95% ³		
Yes	1587 (45.8%)	1615 (46.3%)

	Multivitamins	
	(n=3797)	Placebo (n=3776)
	Mean (SD) or n (%)	Mean (SD) or n (%)
No	1881 (54.2%)	1873 (53.7%)

¹ For participants who were 20 years old or above, underweight, normal weight, overweight, and obesity were defined as BMI <18.5 kg/m², 18.5 to 24.9 kg/m², 25 to 29.9 kg/m², and BMI ≥30 kg/m², respectively. For participants who were <20 years old, World Health Organization BMI-for-age growth references were used to classify adolescents as underweight (<-2 SD), normal weight (-2 SD to <1 SD), overweight (1 SD to <+2 SD) or obese (≥+2 SD).

² Anemia was defined as maternal hemoglobin concentrations <110 g/L.

³ Adherence to the assigned treatment was calculated as the number of tablets that were absent from the returned bottles divided by the total number of tablets the participant should have taken.

Table 2. The effect of prenatal multivitamin supplements on GWG ¹

	Multivitamins (n=3797)	Placebo (n=3776)	P value
Percent adequacy of GWG			
Mean (SD)	96.7% (43.4%)	94.4% (42.5%)	
Mean difference (95% CI) ²	2.3% (0.3%, 4.2%)	Ref.	0.022
Adjusted mean difference (95% CI) ³	2.1% (0.2%, 4.0%)	Ref.	0.029
Inadequate GWG			
N (%)	1881(49.5)	1973 (52.3)	
Relative risk (95% CI) ²	0.95 (0.91, 0.99)	Ref.	0.018
Adjusted relative risk (95% CI) ³	0.95 (0.91, 0.99)	Ref.	0.021
Severely inadequate GWG			
N (%)	910 (24.0)	1005 (26.6)	
Relative risk (95% CI) ²	0.90 (0.83, 0.97)	Ref.	0.008
Adjusted relative risk (95% CI) ³	0.90 (0.84, 0.98)	Ref.	0.010
Excessive GWG			
N (%)	729 (19.2)	672 (17.8)	
Relative risk (95% CI) ²	1.08 (0.98, 1.19)	Ref.	0.12
Adjusted relative risk (95% CI) ³	1.08 (0.98, 1.18)	Ref.	0.12

¹ GWG, gestational weight gain. Inadequate GWG was defined as percent adequacy of GWG < 90%, severely inadequate GWG as percent adequacy of GWG < 70%, and excessive GWG as percent adequacy of GWG > 125%.

² Univariate analysis

³ Adjusted for maternal age, gestational age at enrolment, household wealth index, maternal education, parity, maternal stature, maternal anemia, smoking, and hypertension status.

Table 3. The effect of prenatal multivitamin supplements on GWG ¹ within the second trimester and the third trimester

	the second trimester			the third trimester		
	Multivitamins (n=2568)	Placebo (n=2588)	P value	Multivitamins (n=3150)	Placebo (n=3137)	P value
Percent adequacy of GWG						
Mean (SD)	90.5% (95.4%)	86.5% (92.0%)		92.7% (88.5%)	88.7% (101.9%)	
Mean difference (95% CI) ²	4.0% (-1.1%, 9.1%)	Ref.	0.12	4.0% (-0.7%, 8.7%)	Ref.	0.09
Adjusted mean difference (95% CI) ³	5.0% (-0.5%, 10.5%)	Ref.	0.08	3.6% (-1.5%, 8.8%)	Ref.	0.09
Inadequate GWG						
n(%)	1330 (51.8)	1378 (53.3)		1723 (54.7)	1778 (56.7)	
Relative risk (95% CI) ²	0.97 (0.92, 1.02)	Ref.	0.30	0.97 (0.92, 1.01)	Ref.	0.11
Adjusted relative risk (95% CI) ³	0.97 (0.92, 1.02)	Ref.	0.26	0.96 (0.92, 1.01)	Ref.	0.10
Severely inadequate GWG						
n(%)	999(38.9)	1040 (40.2)		1250 (39.7)	1324 (42.2)	
Relative risk (95% CI) ²	0.97 (0.90, 1.04)	Ref.	0.35	0.94 (0.89, 1.00)	Ref.	0.042
Adjusted relative risk (95% CI) ³	0.97 (0.90, 1.04)	Ref.	0.38	0.94 (0.88, 1.00)	Ref.	0.036

Excessive GWG

n(%)	778 (30.3)	734 (28.4)		865 (27.5)	847 (27.0)	
Relative risk (95% CI) ²	1.06 (0.98, 1.16)	Ref.	0.13	1.02 (0.94, 1.10)	Ref.	0.68
Adjusted relative risk (95% CI) ³	1.07 (0.98, 1.16)	Ref.	0.12	1.01 (0.93, 1.10)	Ref.	0.80

¹ GWG, gestational weight gain. Inadequate GWG was defined as percent adequacy of GWG < 90%, severely inadequate GWG as percent adequacy of GWG < 70%, and excessive GWG as percent adequacy of GWG > 125%.

² Univariate analysis

³ Adjusted for maternal age, gestational age at enrolment, household wealth index, maternal education, parity, maternal stature, maternal anemia, smoking, and hypertension.

Table 4. The effect of prenatal multivitamin supplements on percent adequacy of GWG¹ by potential effect modifiers.

Potential effect modifiers	n	Percent adequacy of GWG			Percent adequacy of GWG during 2nd trimester			Percent adequacy of GWG during 3rd trimester		
		MD (95% CI)	P value	P-int	MD (95% CI)	P value	P-int	MD (95% CI)	P value	P-int
Infant sex										
Female	3,592	3.0% (0.2%,5.8%)	0.04	0.65	3.3% (-4.1%,10.6%)	0.38	0.68	5.4% (-0.8%,11.6%)	0.09	0.55
Male	3,851	2.1% (-0.6%,4.8%)	0.13		5.4% (-1.8%,12.6%)	0.14		2.5% (-4.6%,9.6%)	0.48	
Gestational age at randomization, wk										
<20	2,563	2.3% (-1.4%,6.0%)	0.23	0.99	4.4% (-2.0%,10.8%)	0.17	0.89	-2.3% (-11.8%,7.1%)	0.62	0.07
≥20	5,010	2.2% (0.0%,4.5%)	0.05		3.7% (-4.2%,11.5%)	0.36		6.9% (1.6%,12.2%)	0.01	
Maternal adherence to regimen ²										
<95% adherence	3,202	2.2% (-0.8%,5.3%)	0.15	0.68	5.3% (-2.5%,13.2%)	0.18	0.69	3.2% (-3.6%,10.1%)	0.37	0.38
≥95% adherence	3,754	3.0% (0.4%,5.8%)	0.03		3.2% (-3.8%,10.2%)	0.37		7.3% (1.2%,13.4%)	0.02	
Maternal age, y										
<25	4,227	1.8% (-0.7%,4.3%)	0.17	0.58	5.9% (-0.9%,12.7%)	0.09	0.46	6.1% (-0.7%,13.1%)	0.08	0.33
≥25	3,309	2.9% (-0.2%,5.9%)	0.06		2.0% (-5.8%,9.8%)	0.62		1.5% (-4.8%,7.8%)	0.64	
Parity										
0	3,452	1.5% (-1.3%,4.3%)	0.29	0.44	7.3% (-0.2%,14.7%)	0.06	0.29	5.2% (-2.6%,12.9%)	0.19	0.65
≥1	4,080	3.0% (0.3%,5.7%)	0.03		1.7% (-5.4%,8.7%)	0.64		3.0% (-2.8%,8.8%)	0.32	
BMI at first trimester (observed or imputed) ³										
Underweight	798	3.4% (0.1%,6.7%)	0.05	0.49	7.4% (-3.7%,18.5%)	0.19	0.26	6.6% (-1.9%,15.2%)	0.13	0.40
Normal weight	4,972	1.8% (0.2%,3.5%)	0.03		0.9% (-4.4%,6.2%)	0.74		2.0% (-3.4%,7.3%)	0.47	
Overweight or obesity	1,803	4.3% (-1.3%,9.9%)	0.13		10.7% (-4.0%,25.5%)	0.15		9.3% (-2.9%,21.5%)	0.13	
Maternal stature, cm										
<150	1,191	0.0% (-4.5%,4.5%)	1.00	0.32	3.3% (-8.6%,15.3%)	0.58	0.90	3.0% (-6.5%,12.5%)	0.54	0.84

Potential effect modifiers	n	Percent adequacy of GWG			Percent adequacy of GWG during 2nd trimester			Percent adequacy of GWG during 3rd trimester		
		MD (95% CI)	P value	P-int	MD (95% CI)	P value	P-int	MD (95% CI)	P value	P-int
≥150	6,382	2.7% (0.6%,4.8%)	0.01		4.2% (-1.5%,9.8%)	0.15		4.2% (-1.1%,9.5%)	0.12	
Maternal anemia ⁴										
Yes	4,366	1.2% (-1.2%,3.6%)	0.32	0.12	3.3% (-3.5%,10.2%)	0.35	0.41	2.3% (-4.1%,8.7%)	0.48	0.40
No	2,134	4.8% (0.7%,8.9%)	0.02		8.1% (-1.1%,17.3%)	0.08		7.0% (-1.5%,15.4%)	0.11	
Years of education, y										
≤7	5,860	2.3% (0.2%,4.5%)	0.04	0.75	2.0% (-3.7%,7.7%)	0.50	0.13	5.4% (0.4%,10.3%)	0.03	0.25
≥8	1,678	1.6% (-2.6%,5.8%)	0.46		11.4% (-0.3%,23.0%)	0.06		-1.2% (-13.5%,11.1%)	0.85	
Wealth index <median value										
Yes	3,682	2.4% (-0.2%,5.0%)	0.07	0.89	-0.5% (-7.6%,6.6%)	0.90	0.10	8.3% (2.3%,14.4%)	0.007	0.08
No	3,868	2.1% (-0.7%,5.0%)	0.14		8.0% (0.8%,15.4%)	0.03		0 (-7.0%,7.2%)	0.98	
Hypertension										
Yes	303	1.6% (-10.4%,13.6%)	0.74	0.89	-4.5% (-32.5%,23.5%)	0.74	0.50	5.2% (-22.9%,33.3%)	0.72	0.92
No	7,270	2.3% (0.3%,4.2%)	0.02		4.4% (-0.8%,9.6%)	0.10		4.0% (-0.8%,8.7%)	0.10	
Current smoking										
Yes	20	20.2% (-16.0%,56.4%)	0.26	0.39	28.6% (-78.2%,135.4%)	0.57	0.63	-8.4% (-89.2%,72.5%)	0.83	0.83
No	7,520	2.1% (0.2%,4.1%)	0.03		3.9% (-1.2%,9.1%)	0.14		3.9% (-0.9%,8.6%)	0.11	

¹ GWG, gestational weight gain

² Adherence to the assigned treatment was calculated as the number of tablets that were absent from the returned bottles divided by the total number of tablets the participant should have taken.

³ For participants who were 20 years old or above, underweight, normal weight, overweight, and obesity were defined as BMI <18.5 kg/m², 18.5 to 24.9 kg/m², 25 to 29.9 kg/m², and BMI ≥30 kg/m², respectively. For participants who were <20 years old, World Health Organization BMI-for-age growth references were used to classify adolescents as underweight (<-2 SD), normal weight (-2 SD to <1 SD), overweight (1 SD to <+2 SD) or obese (≥+2 SD).

⁴ Anemia was defined as maternal hemoglobin concentrations <110 g/L.